

PRACTICAL RESEARCH ON THE IMPLICATIONS OF THE START-UP NATION PROGRAM

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Abstract

Purpose – The paper's main objective is to obtain information on the level of satisfaction of the investigated subjects with respect to the financial programs for small and medium enterprises, the main field of the applicants, the access to the online platform with respect to the Start-up Nation program.

Methodology/approach – The research used the boring as method, based on accessibility and the working instrument was the questionnaire.

Findings – Cluj district has developed a lot during the last years and the impact of the Start-up Nation program had a major contribution in the regional economy. Its objectives have been fulfilled through the increase in the number of enterprises, new jobs, the decrease of unemployment and the improvement of the standard of living.

Research limitations/implications – Due to the organizational restrictions related to time, finances and human resources, the sample was 97 subjects who applied for the Start-up Nation program in the Cluj district. The sample method was non-aleatory, based on accessibility, thus we cannot talk about a representative sample, the conclusions being applied only to the investigated sample.

Practical implications – The financing programs for small and medium enterprises are beginning to play an important role in Romania's businesses. The conclusions of the research are important for the Agencies for SMEs, Investment Attraction and Promoting Export because they reveal the perception of the applicants on the program.

Originality/value – The paper presents the results of a totally original research.

Key words: entrepreneurs, Start-up Nation, financing, small and medium enterprises, Cluj district.

Introduction

Most of the studies focus on entrepreneurship and its role in innovation, new businesses and the economic development of the country. Romania's main issue with respect to entrepreneurship is the fact the ratio of start-ups is a high one, but the numbers of those who can make it on long term is much smaller. Even if we register the biggest increase within the European Union, at micro level the incomes include a small number of companies. 4% of the companies are the engine of the economy, while half of them are experiencing difficult times.

The economy of the Cluj district has experienced an accelerated development during the last few years, becoming one of the most dynamic regions in Romania with respect to the contribution to the gross domestic product.

The economy of the Cluj district is based on services and industry, mainly creative industries and IT. More than 15.000 people are working in the IT field. That is why Cluj is called the "Silicon Valley" of Romania.

With the support of the local authorities, business environment, universities and NGOs, Cluj has become an important player in the national economy. An indicator that underlines the involvement and

entrepreneurial spirit is also the number of projects that applied for Start-up Nation 2017 – 2289 business plans.

The hypothesis of the research

Starting from the issue that has to be studied, a series of hypothesis can be elaborated [Bacali et al., 2010, p. 279-280].

- H01: Most of the investigated subjects are satisfied by the financing programs for SMEs.
- H02: The online platform for application has been easy to access for the majority of the respondents
- H03: Production is the main field that has received financing by most of the applicants.
- H04: The non-refundable financial help covers more than 50% of the expenses.
- H05: Most of the applicants are pleased with the information presented on the Agency's site.
- H06: Most of the applicants are pleased with the implementation period of the program.

The instrument of the research

The method that has been used within this research was the boring, and the instrument was the questionnaire.

For the questionnaire, different types of questions have been used [Bacali et al., 2002, p. 31-32]: open questions (addressed to the active process of the subject's memory, verifying and testing what is stable, consolidated in the behavior and knowledge of the subject) and closed questions (dichotomic, multidichotomic and scale responses).

For the elaboration of the questionnaire, the following basic principles have been respected:

- the question should be as short as possible, meanwhile clear and concise;
- the question should be elaborated in such a way that it is avoided a predisposition of the subjects to offer a certain answer;
- the ability of the subjects to answer certain questions has to be taken into account; and
- the question should not be threatening or unpleasant.

The sampling

Due to the organizational restrictions related to time, finances and human resources, the sample was 97 subjects who applied for the Start-up Nation program in the Cluj district. The sample method was non-aleatory, based on accessibility, thus we cannot talk about a representative sample, the conclusions being applied only to the investigated sample.

The results of the research

Further on we will present the level of satisfaction of the SMEs towards the governmental programs. The hypothesis was H01: "Most of the investigated subjects are satisfied by the financing programs for SMEs".

To the question "What is the general satisfaction level with respect to the financing programs for SMEs in Romania?", 41% of the respondents state that they are satisfied, while 9% are completely not satisfied.

The hypothesis is thus confirmed.

Figure 1. The analyses of the satisfaction level of the financing programs for SMEs

The online platform for application has been easy to access according to the majority of the respondents is the hypothesis that the following question was based on. The majority answered that the application was easy to access, for 21 of the investigates subjects it was not easy to access and 14 cannot answer due to the fact that they did not use it. The application has been opened for a few days before the start of the application so that the potential users can test it.

Those 14 subjects who didn't know if the platform was easy to use or not are those who used a consultancy company in order to register the project. The hypothesis is confirmed.

Figure 2. The analyses of the access to the online platform

Within the following question the activity field of the applicants have been investigated. Thus there are 34 enterprises in production, 29 in IT, 26 in services and 8 in creative industries.

Production represents the main field. Out of the 97 respondents, the majority have chosen a business in the production field, an equilibrium being IT and services being noticed, with just 1 company difference. The hypothesis is thus confirmed.

Figure 3. The field of the applicant enterprises

The next question analyses the measure in which the non-refundable financial aid covers the expenses for starting the business. The results show that in 7 cases the expenses are totally covered, 38 of the respondents state that 80% of the expenses have been covered, 35 of them state that they have covered 60% of the expenses and 17 subjects say that the non-refundable aid covered less than 50% of the expenses.

The answers to this question are influenced by the domain of the applicants. Thus, an applicant in the production field has found the funds to be insufficient, while those in the field of services state that the aid covers 100% of the expenses. The hypothesis is confirmed.

Figure 4. The analyses of the level of covering the expenses

“The majority of the investigated subjects are pleased with the information presented on the Agency’s site” has been the hypothesis for the question “How do you appreciate the information on the site?”. 42 of the investigated subjects consider the information to be good, 22 appreciated it with very good, 21 as average, while 9 consider it bad and 3 as very bad. The information that has been available on the site have fulfilled the principle of transparency, a fact proven by the answers of the investigated subjects. The hypothesis is thus confirmed.

Figure 5. The opinion on the website information

The following question was about the period of implementation, starting from the hypothesis that most of the applicants are pleased with it. The answers were as follows: 53 consider it a good one, 22 as a very good period of time, 17 appreciate it as average, 4 as bad and 1 as very bad.

It needs to be mentioned that the implementation period for the project has been a generous one (12 months), which is also proven by the answers ((75 respondents consider it good and very good). The hypothesis is also confirmed.

Figure 6. The analyses of the implementation period

Discussion and conclusions

Cluj district has developed a lot during the last years and the impact of the Start-up Nation program had a major contribution in the regional economy. Its objectives have been fulfilled through the increase in the number of enterprises, new jobs, the decrease of unemployment and the improvement of the standard of living. Most of the applicants have been satisfied by this program and will recommend it to others.

The financing programs for small and medium enterprises are beginning to play an important role in Romania's businesses. The conclusions of the research are important for the Agencies for SMEs, Investment Attraction and Promoting Export because they reveal the perception of the applicants on the program.

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